

APPENDIX B – CHARACTERIZATION OF PARTICIPATING DEVELOPERS AND CHARACTERIZATION OF PARTICIPATING EXTERNAL USERS

DEVELOPERS

Name	Age	Education	Degree	Java Experience	Previous Knowledge of Blockchain
P1	28	Undergraduate	Computer Engineering	2 years	No
P2	31	Undergraduate	Computer Science	2 years	No
P3	33	Master's	Computer Science	7 years	No
P4	26	Undergraduate	Computer Science	1 year	No
P5	28	Undergraduate	Computer Engineering	1 year	No
P6	29	Undergraduate	Computer Science	2 years	No
P7	31	Undergraduate	Computer Science	2 years	No
P8	29	Master's	Computer Engineering	2 years	No
P9	30	Master's	Computer Engineering	6 years	No
P10	27	Undergraduate	Computer Engineering	2 years	No
P11	31	Master's	Computer Engineering	2 years	No
P12	29	Undergraduate	Computer Science	1 year	No
P13	27	Undergraduate	Computer Engineering	2 years	No
P14	33	Master's	Computer Engineering	1 year	No
P15	28	Undergraduate	Computer Engineering	2 years	No

END USERS

Name	Age	Education
P1	30	Undergraduate
P2	38	Undergraduate
P3	50	Undergraduate
P4	30	Undergraduate
P5	41	Undergraduate
P6	37	Undergraduate
P7	42	Undergraduate
P8	58	Undergraduate
P9	60	Undergraduate
P10	55	Undergraduate